

IMPORTANCE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TRAINING QUALIFIED OFFICERS

B.A.Akhmadzhanov

Associate professor of the Academy of the Armed Forces,
doctor of philosophy in Military Sciences (PhD):
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Abstract: The use of smart technology in the classroom further enhances the intellectual potential and scientific and theoretical knowledge of the students. At the same time, the introduction of information and communication technologies and modern pedagogical technologies in education will lead to further enrichment and improvement of education.

Keywords: education, information technology, informatics, innovation, pedagogical technology.

The concept emerged in the 20th century and was applied in the 1940s-1950s in the style of "educational technology", meaning the use of audio-visual techniques in the educational process. The term initially began to be used in the United States. Later, the use of the term "programmed education" became widespread in the "technology of education" industry. Then pedagogical technology-designed education and began to express the educational process aimed at a specific goal. In the 80s of the last century, pedagogical technology began to be used synonymously with computer and Information Technology. Of the issues that have attracted the attention of pedagogical scientists and teachers in the following decades, is pedagogical technology (PT). The fact that this topic is intensely studied in scientific works, reports, special periodicals, causes controversy also testifies to how important its place in education/ concentration of available materials, analysis of its theoretical and practical concepts on the basis of the requirements of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education and the National Program of Personnel Training, ultimately, trying to create an empirical basis

Since the years of the series, pedagogical technology has come to be seen as the implementation of the educational process using technical means. Only from the 70s did this concept begin to be interpreted in a new way in pedagogical literature. By technology. as a result of the effect shown to the object from subject to M moment, the process leading to qualitative changes in the subject is understood. The technology always envisions using the necessary tools and conditions to perform objective actions directed at the object in a specific sequence.

At a time when the reform of the system of continuing education in our country, that is, the reorganization of the educational and educational process on the basis of educational standards, special attention is paid to the activities of the teacher, his pedagogical skills, since it is the teacher who is considered the creator of the perfect generation. One of the principles enshrined in the Education Act and the National Training Program is to identify the capable and talented among young people and ensure their comprehensive maturation. At all stages of the educational system, great attention should be paid to the development of creative talents of young people one of the main tasks of teachers is to promote the initiative of young people

to be able to see innovative ideas and thoughts, talents and talents in a timely manner and realize it. Young people are required to educate leading young people with high morale through the development of organizational skills and managerial skills, to guide them for the development of our country and its prospects. The problems of the teacher's application of innovative technologies, which have recently been widely introduced in universities, and the prospects for its solution, are becoming an urgent problem. This is due to the fact that it is necessary to have professional knowledge inherent in pedagogical activity, to prepare and adapt to independent pedagogical activity and social relations, including in the structure of the pedagogical community. Application, creation and management of innovative technologies in vocational-oriented training, through which education and upbringing solve today's current tasks. Therefore, the search for pedagogical innovation is an alternative to the goal of determining the order in which learning, through analysis, selects the most effective ones and applies them to practice. Therefore, the teacher is looking for ways, methods and methods, forms of training and tools that activate the student, which are convenient for him and the learner, improving them.

The higher the degree of interactivity, the more productive the educational process will be. Relevance of the teaching situation: the most common and characteristic educational methods are considered: conversation, argument, game, case study, method of projects, problem method, mental attack, etc. The organization of the educational process, the achievement of an effective result largely depends on the choice of the right, optimal method. When choosing the most convenient and high-performing method, the teacher is required to evaluate several factors, analyze them and, on the basis of this assumption, have the qualification of choosing a method suitable for a particular situation. It is an extremely important issue for future teachers to formulate the qualification of choosing the most convenient method suitable for each lesson. Because a correctly selected method leads to the fact that the learning process is effective. Smart technology encourages students to experiment, construct models, independently create music and movies, implement their own ideas, and create products. This approach to teaching allows children to effectively learn theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Increases the creativity of students, becomes a solid foundation in the training of highly qualified, modern personnel. It is advisable to carry out the following measures to introduce Smart technologies into the educational system of our country in the future: the time allotted for technological update (2020-2025) is very short. Therefore, to use the "Quick start" method, that is, to study the requirements of the Smart education educational environment and accelerate the introduction into the educational system of our country; to establish, coordinate and systematically create electronic resources from different disciplines in our republic in accordance with the world's templates, as well as to create, as far as possible, in cooperation with other countries, in accordance with the general educational environment; to translate and adapt the most optimal of them, without recreating other open resources created around the world, and to introduce educational institutions Modern society is an information society that is characterized by the development of computer technology and communication media, making things and devices around it more and more "smart" and making life more comfortable, safe and interesting.

This stage of development of society and the economy is characterized by:

- increase the role of information, knowledge and Information Technology in the life of society;

- increase in the number of people engaged in the production of Information Technology, Communication and information products and services;

- to expand the informatization of society using telephone, radio, television, internet, traditional and electronic media; - to create a global information space that provides effective information exchange of people, their use of World Information Resources, meeting the needs of information products and services.

The Terms "new order", "innovation process" are exactly similar, that is, have the same meaning. Innovation has been coming side by side with it for the long period since the emergence of educational practice to bring innovations to it, to target the existing educational structure, to raise quality at the cost of introducing elements of transformation, evolutionism and improvement, sometimes justative, and sometimes broad commas. Innovation is the practical use of technical, technological inventions and achievements. It represents an innovation in education as a pedagogical category. The novelty is often inherent in the introduction and application of new methods, methods, tools, new concepts, new training programs, methods of training, etc. In the following decades, such concepts as "pedagogical technology", "progressive pedagogical Technology", "Technology of new information" are found in the created, pedagogical-distorted literature. However, they have not been fully defined to date. Pedagogical scientists and practitioners of our republic strive to create educational technologies that are scientifically based and adapted to the socio-pedagogical conditions of Uzbekistan and apply them in educational and educational practice. All this made reforms in education a major issue. In solving these issues, the law "on education" and the "National Training Program" respond in every way.

At the same time, modern pedagogical technology — on the basis of systematic approaches—demonstrates the interaction of human potential and technical means necessary to facilitate the forms of training, guarantee its result and objectively assess. The method, methods and tools used in the processes of clarification of educational goals, training and mastering, diversification of methods and tools, deepening the content of educational and educational processes—all this means improving the activities of educational institutions. However, it is said that there is no limit to improvement, that is, no end. After that, both pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills are limitless concepts. The more it is researched in this regard and the more initiative it is—the less it seems. This is also the simplest and Main fact of teaching. Teacher (educator) limiting only his activities in this taxiing will ultimately lead to the fulfillment of a high social order.

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